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“THE REAL WITCHES”

They are everywhere, lurking around.
They want to devour every piece of you,
Their presence pierces like a needle.
To your bleeding chest.

Your head spins when they're near.
No matter how you try to feel warmth toward them.
They will devour your peace, your joy, and your freedom.
And you would wish to cut every thread that ties you.
But you never know how to break free.

They were never invited into your lives.
They are like leeches, they cling to you.
They take, they never give, and never satisfied.
Their hands beg out like you owed them.
Their words taste of poison and rust.

They are thieves of the happiness you deserve,
Twisting it into something hellish.
They demand more and more,
As if your sacrifices were owed to them.

Their generational curses are not yours to inherit.
Their bitterness will not stain your lives.
They want everything you have,
As if it were built for them.
They forced you to open your darkness,
Their presence is the thorn in your side, suffocating.
They tainted your days with resentment.

They have stolen enough from you!
It has to stop! You have to silently let go.
Step out of their dark shadow, into your bright light.
Break free from the real witches!